

Metadata for publication	The Meaning of Emoji to Describe Food Experiences in Pre-Adolescents
Acknowledgement	This project was conducted as part of the project “Edulia-Bringing down barriers to children's healthy eating”, which has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 764985.
Publication	The article is published online 16.09.20 (open-access) and the DOI https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9091307
Metadata for data access	
Data summary	-
Naming	-
Type of data	-
For data that is not completely anonymized, briefly describe (1) if and where it is registered that the data contains personal data, and (2) whether and how a Privacy Impact Assessment (PIA) was conducted	-
Software used for analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • XLSTAT (version 2018.7, Addinsoft, New York, NY, USA) • RStudio (version 1.1.456, 2016, RStudio, Inc., Boston, MA, USA)
For raw data in physical form (paper-pencil survey, etc.) please specify where this is stored and for how long this will be the case	The publication does not contain raw data in physical form.